

Legal Recognition of Shadow Directors of Companies in Tanzania: Exploring the Options

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Abstract:

Companies being abstract persons depend on natural persons to manage their daily transactions. Such individuals are called company directors. According to the Companies Act of 2002, the minimum numbers of directors in single and multiple membership companies are one and two respectively. The Act further mandates that their consent has to be filed with the Registrar of Companies. Directors are regarded as the brain of the company, as they control what it does. However, at times, the class of directors known as shadow directors, who have a latent stake in the company may indirectly control it. These individuals operate from behind the scene thereby raising the possibility of misconduct and unethical dealings. In severe cases, these can extend to tax evasion, corruption and money laundering, committed in circumstances which may create opportunities for them to escape accountability or liability. The absence of a robust legal framework on the identification and accountability of shadow directors seems to be an issue in many developing countries, including Tanzania. This paper through doctrinal research methodology examines the potential reliance on the Beneficial Ownership (BO) rules in identifying such shadow directors in Tanzania. It also draws upon the experiences of other common law countries. The paper concludes that rules on BO can help to identify shadow directors in Tanzania despite the absence of an express provision on shadow directors in the Companies' Act. However, a long-term solution is to revise the law to incorporate shadow directors.

Keywords: Companies, Law, Beneficial Ownership, Shadow Director, Tanzania.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Company directors are the individuals who are entrusted with the responsibility for the day-to-day activities of a company.¹ Persons who occupy the position of directorship may be ascribed different names, for example, managers or governors. However, the central point is that they direct, control and oversee the operations of the company.² They are regarded as the brain of the company owing to the supervisory and directing roles they play in relation to the affairs of the company.³ Although corporate law generally recognizes registered companies as persons in law, they are actually abstract beings.⁴ However, abstract persons cannot manage their own affairs or attain the objectives of the company as provided for under the memorandum and articles of associations, which are the key documents upon which companies are registered. Additionally, being a person in law, a company stands separate from its members and those who manage its affairs, such that, they cannot be held accountable for its liabilities.⁵

The Companies Act of 2002, which regulates companies in Tanzania requires single and multiple membership companies to have a minimum number of one and two directors respectively.⁶ Moreover, those who aspire to become directors of a company have to submit their particulars and a form indicating their consent to so be appointed to the Office of the Registrar of Companies (ORCs).⁷ Consequently, the ORCs is always update with the names and particulars of persons appointed directors of companies. However, there are several other parties who have interests or stakes in the company such as members or shareholders, creditors and even suppliers. Although directors are appointed to manage the day-to-day affairs of the company, other individuals with vested interest may indirectly exert influence and control on the directors. This category of persons who exert influence and control over the actual directors of the company are known as shadow directors.

A shadow director may be distinguished from a *de facto* director in three ways. Firstly, the shadow director does not pose and or even claim to be a director, whereas a defector director does.⁸ Although a mere holding out is not the sole ground to prove that one is a

¹ Tanzania, 'The Companies Act' (2002). s. 181.

² Capital Market and Securities Authority, 'Guideline on Corporate Governance Practices by Public Listed Companies in Tanzania.' (Capital Market and Securities Authority, 2002). para 3.1. ; See also, Charles Wild and Stuart Weinstain, *Smith and Keenan's Company Law*, 15th ed. (London: Pearson, 2011). p. 334.

³ House of Lords, *Bolton (Engineering) Co Ltd v TJ Graham & Co Ltd*, No. 1 QB (House of Lords 1957). p. 172.; The Supreme Court -UK, *Holland v The Commissioner for Her Majesty's Revenue and Customs and another*, No. UKSC 51 (UK SC 2010). para 115.

⁴ *Solomon v Solomon and Company Ltd* (AC 1897) 22.

⁵ *ibid*

⁶ Tanzania, The Companies Act. s. 186.

⁷ Tanzania, The Companies Act. No. 12 of 2002 s 210(1), (2) (a-b); Tanzania, 'The Finance Act', No. 8 of 2020. s 451A(b)(iii).

⁸ Andrew Keay, Peter Walton, and Joseph Curl, *Corporate Governance and Insolvency: Accountability and Transparency* (Cheltenham: Edward Elgar Publishing Limited, 2022). para 1.042.

de facto director, nevertheless, it corroborates other elements.⁹ Secondly, while a shadow director is not appointed by the company, a *de facto* director may actually be appointed by the company and undertakes the duties of directors in the company.¹⁰ At times, although formally appointed, a *de facto* director, may not have actually met the full requirements for appointment such as holding of shares, qualifications and or age.¹¹ Thirdly, acts of a *de facto* director binds the company as if he is actually a director but not those of a shadow director. On this issue, the law in Tanzania states that that the acts of a director or manager shall be valid notwithstanding any defect that may afterwards be discovered in his appointment or qualification.¹²

Running the affairs of companies indirectly or by proxies may raise the suspicion of unscrupulous activities like crime, tax evasion, and money laundering, or even provide a cover for them.¹³ It is worth noting that the veil of incorporation will be lifted to identify and hold personally responsible, persons who use companies to defraud creditors, members, suppliers, and so on. In other words, such persons will be personally accountable.¹⁴ Here, rules of separate corporate personality are ignored. Similarly, individuals who direct the affairs of companies behind the shadows will be held accountable. On this issue, Mathew Aitken is of the view that:

Being a shadow director can lead to serious legal consequences. Even though the person has not been officially appointed, they may still be held accountable for a company's failings, particularly in cases of insolvency, fraud, or breach of directors' duties. If a court finds that someone has been acting as a shadow director, they could be disqualified from acting as a director in the future, face personal financial liability, or be prosecuted under company or insolvency law. This risk applies even if the person was not fully aware of the legal status they had taken on.¹⁵

⁹ High Court of Republic of Singapore, *Cheng Tim Jin v Alvamar Capital Pte. Ltd*, No. SGHC 220 (High Court of Republic of Singapore 2019). para 14.

¹⁰ *Re-Hydrodam (Corby) Ltd*, No. 2 BCLC 180 (1994). 180, pp 4-6; High Court of Republic of Singapore, *Cheng Tim Jin v Alvamar Capital Pte. Ltd*. para 16.

¹¹ *Re-Hydrodam (Corby) Ltd*, No. 2 BCLC 180 (1994). 180 pp.4-6

¹² Tanzania, *The Companies Act*. No. 12 of 2002 s 189.

¹³ *Ibid* s 383.

¹⁴ *Ibid* s. 384.

¹⁵ Mathew Aitken, 'What Is a Shadow Director?', *The 1st Blog* (blog), 14 April 2025, <https://www.1stformations.co.uk/blog/shadow-director/>. (Accessed on April 2025)

However, weak legal frameworks, in many developing countries, including Tanzania, make it harder to identify shadow directors and curb potentials of fraudulent activities. This may be expounded in two ways. Firstly, many countries rely upon companies as a common vehicle through which trade and business activities are carried on.¹⁶ This means an exponential increase in the number of registered companies is expected. For example, by the years 2020 and 2024, about 4,000,000 and 219,000 companies were registered in the United Kingdom and Tanzania respectively.¹⁷ Secondly, some of the companies are huge and tend to use complex structures which in turn add to the complex manner in which they are managed and controlled.¹⁸ Consequently, in the absence of proper oversight and regulations, unscrupulous individuals who operate as shadow directors, may escape liability when things go wrong in the companies over which they have exercised control.¹⁹ This paper tries to answer the question, to what extent can the legal framework on beneficial ownership (BO) in Tanzania be relied upon to identify shadow directors with the view to guarantee accountability in the business environment?²⁰

This paper is organized into five major sections. This first section presents the introduction to this paper, while the second section offers conceptual clarifications and the essence of BO rules in the modern corporate business environment. Section three presents the main arguments aimed at answering the research question in section one above, while section four offers a way forward to Tanzania. The last concludes the paper.

2. CONCEPTUAL CLARIFICATION AND ESSENCES OF BO RULES

This section presents two main sub-sections. The first sub-section descriptively, presents the two key concepts namely, shadow directors and Beneficial Owners (BOs). This is vital owing to the possible variety of ways such concepts may be used. The second sub-section presents the essence of BO rules in the modern corporate business environment.

2.1 Clarification of concepts

The general business laws in Tanzania lack an express provision on shadow directors. In particular, even laws regulating companies' BO which are relatively new in Tanzania

¹⁶ Keay, Walton, and Curl, *Corporate Governance and Insolvency: Accountability and Transparency*. (Cheltenham: Edward Elgar Publishing Limited, 2022) para 1.001.

¹⁷ Keay, Walton, and Curl. para 1.005.; Tanzania National Bureau of Statistics, '2023/24 Tanzania Statistical Business Register Census' (Tanzania National Bureau of Statistics, 2024), <https://microdata.nbs.go.tz/index.php/catalog/46/related-materials#:~:text=Census%20results%20indicates%20that%2C%20a%20total%20of,inTanzania%20Mainland%20and%2040%2C175%20in%20Tanzania%20Zanzibar.> (Accessed on April 2025).

¹⁸ Keay, Walton, and Curl, *Corporate Governance and Insolvency: Accountability and Transparency*. (Cheltenham: Edward Elgar Publishing Limited, 2022), para 1.006.

¹⁹ Edith Nyabicha, Philip Nyakundi, and Dennis Kabai, 'How Regional Frameworks Can Be Leveraged to Facilitate the Implementation or Operationalization of Beneficial Ownership Reforms at Regional and Country Level (EAC, ECOWAS, SADC, COMESA)' (Global Financial Integrity, 2024). p.2.

²⁰ Tanzania, The Finance Act. No 8 of 2020; United Republic of Tanzania, 'The Companies (Beneficial Ownership) Regulations' (2021).

suffer from the same shortfall. According to Michael Hobson, the term shadow director is better defined through its key elements namely, that it must be a natural person, there must be validly appointed directors of the company, that the appointed directors are accustomed to manage the affairs of the company based on advice received from this person, and that this person is neither a professional adviser nor a hired independent expert.²¹

Luckiness Jangu also relies on the same elements in defining the term shadow director since the Tanzanian Company's Act is silent on this.²² As such, the definition adopted under the Companies Act in Tanzania seems too restrictive. The Act defines the term director to mean any person who will be occupying the position of a director irrespective of the name they may be assigned.²³ This means that anyone who occupies a formal position and issues directives upon which the affairs of the company are managed is regarded as a director. However, the absence of a clear definition of a shadow director appears to not only limit the possibility of identifying and holding them accountable but also distinguishing them from other types of directors such as *de facto* directors. Jangu has provided a working definition of the term shadow director as follows:

Shadow directors are persons who are not actually appointed directors but whose advice is followed by the actual directors in whole.²⁴

The Companies Act of the United Kingdom (UK) is more advanced than the law in Tanzania since it has a relevant provision which defines the term shadow directors. It may be argued here that her level of economic development which is also evidenced by a large number of registered companies that are used as vehicle for socio-economic activities is behind these advancements.²⁵ The Act states as that:

“Shadow director”, in relation to a company, means a person in accordance with whose directions or instructions the directors of the company are accustomed to act.²⁶

²¹ Michael Hobson, ‘The Law of Shadow Directorships’, *Bond Law Review* 10, No. 2 (1998). p. 203.

²² Luckness Jangu, ‘The Qualification of Company Directors and the Performance of Companies in Tanzania: Critical Analysis of the Companies Act, 2002’ (Morogoro, Tanzania, Mzumbe University, 2012). p. 36.

²³ Tanzania, The Companies Act. s 2.

²⁴ Jangu, ‘The Qualification of Company Directors and the Performance of Companies in Tanzania: Critical Analysis of the Companies Act, 2002’. p.36.

²⁵ See para 1 above.

²⁶ United Kingdom, ‘Companies Act’ (2006). s. 251 (1).

The Kenyan Companies Act expressly provides for a shadow director because it defines the term director to mean:

Any person in accordance with whose directions or instructions (not being advice given in a professional capacity) the directors of the body are accustomed to act.²⁷

To distinguish shadow directors from potentially others who relate with, and or give advice to the company, the laws in UK and Kenya exclude all professional advisers and any holding company in relation to advice it gives to its subsidiary.²⁸ Consequently, when the board of directors of a holding company controls the subsidiary company, members of the board of directors of the controlling or holding company are not regarded as shadow directors. However, definitions and or elements given by Jangu and the UK's Act seem silent on the nature and extent of the reliance by the actual directors on the advice from the shadow directors.

In addition, Colin Moore, uses the same elements (as Jangu and the UK Act) to define shadow directors but with some modification.²⁹ According to Moore, a shadow director should be a person who greatly influences the decision of the company; he should control a substantial area of the company such that he is regarded as a legitimate controller of the company.³⁰ It is worth noting that Moore formulated this definition of the term shadow director with the view to hold them accountable under the directors' fiduciary duties.³¹

It is argued that other stakeholders in the company may have rights to protect their interests in the company without necessarily being regarded as shadow directors.³² Creditors for example, whose interest would be in jeopardy if the affairs of the company are not properly managed may hardly remain calm without exerting pressure on the management of the company.³³ Should they be regarded as shadow directors? Certainly

²⁷ Republic of Kenya, 'Companies Act', 17 § (2015). S 3(1).

²⁸ United Kingdom, Companies Act. s 251 (2-3).

²⁹ Colin Moore, 'Obligations in the Shade: The Application of Fiduciary Director's Duties to Shadow Directors.', *Legal Studies* 36, no. 2 (2016). p. 352.

³⁰ Moore Colin, 'Obligations in the Shade: The Application of Fiduciary Director's Duties to Shadow Directors.', *Legal Studies* 36, No. 2 (2016).p. 352.

³¹ *Ibid* p. 352.

³² Neil Jameison and Kelly Hughes, 'The Identification of Shadow Directors under the English Law: What Guidance Might Buzzle Provide?', *Butterworth Journal of International Banking and Financial Law*, 27, No 10 (2012). p.366.;Financial Action Task Force, 'Beneficial Ownership of a Legal Person' (Financial Action Task Force, 2023), http://www.fatf-gafi.org/publications/FATFrecommendations/guidance-beneficial-ownership-legal_persons.html. pp.18-19, (Accessed on January 2025)

³³ J Neil Jameison and Kelly Hughes, 'The Identification of Shadow Directors under the English Law: What Guidance Might Buzzle Provide?', *Butterworth Journal of International Banking and Financial Law*, 27, No 10 (2012) p. 366.

not. To exemplify this, creditors with convertible bond for example, may have power to influence the management of the company under their agreement.³⁴

With reference to the common law, the term shadow director has been extensively analyzed. In the case of *Re-Hydrodam (Corby) Ltd*, the court was of the view that in situations where a parent company is regarded as a director of its subsidiary company, then its directors do not automatically become shadow director there too.³⁵ The court went further to state that, to establish whether a shadow director exists, primarily there must be those who are appointed and occupying the position of directors in a company. Other criteria include:

- a) The fact that the alleged person must have directed those directors on how to manage the company;
- b) The fact that the directors complied with the directions from the alleged person; and
- c) The fact that such directors are accustomed to rely on the advice of the alleged person.³⁶

There are people who may exert pressure on the directors of the company and influence how the companies may be managed without necessarily being referred to as directors. A good example could be creditors who might have such rights under a particular agreement. On this situation, the court in the case of *Buzzle Operations Pty Ltd vs Apple Computers Australia Pty Ltd*³⁷ stated:

I agree that influence exercised on directors of a company by a mortgagee acting in its own interests, particularly if supported by contractual rights in its mortgage documents, would not generally constitute the mortgagee a shadow director.³⁸

In particular, shadow directors are not liable to acts of the directors of the company at the time when they were not advising them. They are also not liable if they offered advice,

³⁴ Financial Action Task Force, 'Beneficial Ownership of a Legal Person' (Financial Action Task Force, 2023), http://www.fatf-gafi.org/publications/FATFrecommendations/guidance-beneficial-ownership-legal_persons.html. pp.18-19, (Accessed on January 2025)". pp. 18-19.

³⁵*Re-Hydrodam (Corby) Ltd*, No. 2 BCLC 180 (1994). 180

³⁶ *Re-Hydrodam (Corby) Ltd*, No. 2 BCLC 180 (1994). 180. pp. 4-6.

³⁷ New South Wales Court of Appeal, *Buzzle Operations Pty Ltd (in liq) v Apple Computer Australia Pty Ltd*, No. 109 (New South Wales Court of Appeal (NSWCA) 2011).

³⁸ *ibid* p. 7.

which was not acted upon by the directors of the company. This implies that the directors need to habitually act on advice from the shadow directors before the shadow directors can incur liability.³⁹ The court decision further shows that a person does not cease to be a shadow director even if the directors of the company are left with some discretionary powers to comply with their instructions, as long as there is a proven link between the advice given by the shadow director and the directors of the company.⁴⁰

Therefore, a shadow director is defined by establishing the primary ground that there cannot be a shadow director if there is no one legally appointed as a director, or who is a *de facto* for a company. Other qualifying elements of a shadow director are that:

- i. He must be a natural person who is not actually appointed as a director of a company;
- ii. That this person does not stand as;
 - a. A professional adviser;
 - b. A holding company in relation to its subsidiary, nor
 - c. A stakeholder in the company (who Exerts influence on the appointed directors subject to laws and rights accruing from his relation to the company).
- iii. But upon whose advice, the company directors are accustomed to rely to a large extent in managing the affairs of the company irrespective of potential discretionary powers they are left with.

This working definition of a shadow director is derived from the preceding analysis of scholarly and textual examination of the term. According to the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) and Inter-American Development Bank, the term BO is defined to mean:

A natural person who ultimately owns or controls a legal entity or arrangements such as company, trust or foundation.⁴¹

³⁹ Ibid. para 248.

⁴⁰ Ibid para 247.

⁴¹ Inter-American Development Bank ('IDB'), Organisation for Economic, and Cooperation and Development("OECD"), 'A Beneficial Ownership Implementation Toolkit' (OECD, 2019), https://publications.iadb.org/publications/english/document/A_Beneficial_Ownership_Implementation_Toolkit_en_en.pdf. p.3. (Accessed on January 2025)

The definition is relevant owing to the fact that it links the BO with ownership and control of the company. While it may seem reasonable to state that he who owns a company will have the power to control it, the definition seems silent on the nature of control of the company. Control can either be either direct or indirect control; the later signaling shadow directorship. In an attempt to recognize BO situations in the corporate world, the legal definition of a BO in Tanzania has highlighted the possible forms of control:

- a) A person who directly or indirectly ultimately owns or exercises substantial control over an entity or an arrangement;
- b) A person who exercises significant control or influence over a person or arrangement through a formal or informal agreement.⁴²

Consequently, BO is currently expected to revolutionize and guarantee greater transparency in the world of corporate businesses. It does so by identifying natural persons who are truly owners, direct or indirect controllers, and actual receivers of the economic benefits accruing from corporate businesses.⁴³ This in turn, safeguards the interest of corporate stakeholders against potential fraudsters who abuse their control of the management of a company to commit fraud.

2.2 Essence of BO rules in the modern corporate business environment

It has been pointed out that unscrupulous individuals may rely upon corporate entities and use them as a mask for fraudulent activities.⁴⁴ In Uganda for example, it is estimated that every year the country loses more than USD 500 million through illicit business activities such as money laundering and tax evasion.⁴⁵ It is argued that allowing corporate business activities to run anonymously provides a sanctuary for illicit activities in many countries that do not have laws on Beneficial Ownership (BO).⁴⁶

⁴² Tanzania, The Finance Act. No. 8 of 2020, s 7.

⁴³ Kaisa de Bel, Onesmus Mugenyi, and Jmaes Muhindo, 'Corporate Transparency: A Guide for Beneficial Ownership Laws in Uganda' (The Global Financial Integrity, 2022). p.5; United Republic of Tanzania, The Companies (Beneficial Ownership)Regulations. (2021)

⁴⁴ See the introduction to this paper above.

⁴⁵ Bel, Mugenyi, and Muhindo, 'Corporate Transparency: A Guide for Beneficial Ownership Laws in U Bel, Kaisa de, Onesmus Mugenyi, and Jmaes Muhindo. 'Corporate Transparency: A Guide for Beneficial Ownership Laws in Uganda'. The Global Financial Integrity, 2022'. p. 5.

⁴⁶ Inter-American Development Bank ('IDB'), Organisation for Economic, and Cooperation and Development("OECD"), 'A Beneficial Ownership Implementation Toolkit' (OECD, 2019), https://publications.iadb.org/publications/english/document/A_Beneficial_Ownership_Implementation_Toolkit_en_en.pdf. p.3. (Accessed on January 2025) p.4.

Many developing countries are adopting legal frameworks that guarantee broad-based socio-economic empowerment of their citizens.⁴⁷ In Tanzania for example, majority of the local citizens who are poor are not formally linked with economic activities that can empower them economically.⁴⁸ To guarantee broad-based socio-economic empowerment, laws on BO are desirable. It has been observed that a legal framework that is silent on BO provides an environment where socio-economic benefits which were meant for the poor majority are appropriated by a few rich elites through registered companies.⁴⁹ One of the ways by which this can be done is to hide the identity of the real owners of corporate entities, while other individuals act as their proxies on the official registration documents of the companies.

A proper definition of the term BO unlocks many unethical business practices which include lengthy chains of business entities which may extend beyond the borders of one country; and the use of nominee or bearers' shares.⁵⁰ These business practices are used to defraud the real owners of companies or beneficiaries in countries with lax corporate rules. Although laws may not prohibit or limit the number of countries in which companies may invest, they actually may be used to limit the use of nominees and bearers' shares, which do not disclose actual beneficiaries.⁵¹ If an individual owns the majority of the shares in a company under the bearers' shares, he automatically has the power to influence the management of the company through the power of appointing or removing directors. BOs also aim to disclose the identities of individuals who directly or indirectly control the management of companies, so as to hold them accountable in the event of wrongdoing.

In any democratic state, socio-economic development is secured through laws regulating investments in various sectors of the economy.⁵² If there are challenges such as illicit activities, money laundering or tax evasion, legal reforms are used to catalyze the change. New laws may be passed, or new oversight or regulatory bodies may be established. An

⁴⁷ Republic of South Africa, 'Broad-Based Black Economic Empowerment Act', 53 § (2003).; Zimbabwe, 'Indigenisation and Economic Empowerment Act', 14 § (2007). ;URT, 'The National Economic Empowerment Act', 16 § (2004).

⁴⁸ Baraza la Taifa la Uwezeshaji Kiuchumi, 'Taarifa Ya Utekelezaji Was Sera Ya Taifa Ya Uwezeshaji Wnaanchi Kiuchumi Ya Mwaka 2004 Katika Kipindicha Kuanzia Julai 2022 Hadi Juni 2023.' (Dodoma: Baraza la Taifa la Uwezeshaji Wananchi Kiuchumi, 2023). para 4.2.4.1/2.

⁴⁹ John Ombella, "'FRONTING" a Threat to the Local Empowerment Schemes in Tanzania: Legal and Policy Analysis', *The Open University Law Journal* 6, No. 1 (2015).

⁵⁰ Inter-American Development Bank ('IDB'), Organisation for Economic, and Cooperation and Development("OECD"), 'A Beneficial Ownership Implementation Toolkit' (OECD, 2019), https://publications.iadb.org/publications/english/document/A_Beneficial_Ownership_Implementation_Toolkit_en_en.pdf. (Accessed on January 2025) p.5.

⁵¹ Ibid. pp.5-6.

⁵² Vibhute Khushal and Aynalem Filipos, 'Legal Research Methods: Teaching Material' (Justice and Legal System Research Institute, 2009). p.6.; John Ombella, 'Safeguarding Rights to Clean Water and Food Security for Mine-Host Communities: Analysis of Tanzania's Compliance with International Standards' ((PhD) Law, Dar es Salaam, Open University of Tanzania, 2022), <https://repository.out.ac.tz/3764/>. pp. 66-67. (Accessed on February 2024)

example may be derived from Colombia which faced illicit financial activities.⁵³ To address the problem, a law was enacted and an institution established to deal with the illicit activities.⁵⁴

3.0 CAN COMPANY BENEFICIAL OWNERSHIP RULES BE RELIED UPON TO IDENTIFY SHADOW DIRECTORS?

It has already been said that Tanzania suffers from the absence of express legal provisions on the shadow director.⁵⁵ It is further noted that those who have ill-minded individuals may capitalize upon this lacuna to control the affairs of the company for their personal benefit.⁵⁶ This part reviews the principles under BO as promulgated under various business laws in Tanzania. This section of the article draws upon the experiences of some common law countries such like the United Kingdom, South Africa, Kenya and Nigeria. Two reasons are advanced for the choosing these jurisdictions. Firstly, they have more advanced legislations than Tanzania to address the present realities of the corporate world. Secondly, they are common law countries with comparable legislations and legal histories. Generally, among common law countries, the principles of judicial precedent and *stare decisis* can be transplanted or borrowed to address legal loopholes.⁵⁷ For law to successfully tackle a legal problem, it should not only define the problem, but also establish procedures for dealing with it.⁵⁸ Based on these two criteria, the shadow directorship is examined as a legal problem. An attempt is made to resolve this problem using the rules on beneficial ownership.

3.1 By defining degrees in which beneficial ownership transpires

As shadow directors do not directly or expressly hold themselves out as directors or claim to be directors, it may be difficult to notice them. Consequently, their influence on the manner in which the company is managed is indirect. Although Tanzania does not have an express provision on shadow director as it is in the UK law, it is still possible through the new law on BO to identify them for accountability purposes.⁵⁹ The preceding definition of BO identifies individuals with indirect ownership rights in a company. It also identifies individuals who greatly and indirectly influences the manner in which the

⁵³ Katherine Alfonso and Julia Yansura, 'Columbia's New Regulatory Framework for Beneficial Ownership: Analysis of Strengths and Weaknesses' (The Global Financial Integrity, 2022). p.1.

⁵⁴ Alfonso and Yansura. p.1.

⁵⁵ See the introduction section of this paper above

⁵⁶ Ibid

⁵⁷United Republic of Tanzania, 'Judicature and Application of Laws Act', Pub. L. No. 358 (2002). s 2 (3) ;Geoffrey Wilson, 'Comparative Legal Scholarship', in *Research Methods for Law*, ed. Michael McConville (Edinburgh: Edinburgh University Press, 2007).p. 98; Stephen Hall, 'Researching International Law', in *Research Methods for Law*, ed. Michael McConville (Edinburgh University Press, 2007). p.199.

⁵⁸ Alfonso, Katherine, and Julia Yansura. 'Columbia's New Regulatory Framework for Beneficial Ownership: Analysis of Strengths and Weaknesses'. (The Global Financial Integrity, 2022) para 1.

⁵⁹ See the UK cited law under para 2 above (Companies Act 2006)

company is controlled.⁶⁰ Persons who fall into these categories are recognized by law even when the agreement between them is appears to be loose or informal.⁶¹

There are formal procedures to register all persons who are willing to become directors of companies. However, when one intends to become a shadow director, such procedures will not be followed instead an informal agreement between the registered director and the shadow director may regulate their relation. In particular, the regulations states that:

Anyone who directly, or indirectly ultimately owns or exercises substantial control over an entity or an arrangement.

A similar but a more direct provision may be borrowed from South African law that shows that rules on BOs may also be relied to identify the shadow directors, as here under stated:

A person who] gives directions or instructions to a juristic person that has a beneficial interest in that security, and its directors or the trustees are accustomed to act in accordance with that person's directions or instructions.⁶²

Consequently, the legal requirement to register those in control under informal agreements and those whose instructions actual directors are accustomed to act intends to uncover shadow directors with the view to hold them accountable.

3.2 By the registration of nature and extent of beneficial interest

Registration of persons with interest in the affairs of a company has been regulated under the Companies Act in various ways. Companies are required to maintain a register of its members in its registered office.⁶³ Generally, members expect to benefit from the company when it makes profit. The profit of the company is shared among its members' subject to their shareholding.⁶⁴ With respect to other stakeholders such as creditors, dual registration is required instead. Dual registration here represents firstly the requirement of the company to maintain a register of all charges affecting its assets in its registered office.⁶⁵ Secondly, either the company or the creditor may register all charges affecting the assets of the company with the ORCs.⁶⁶ Creditors of the company benefit from the

⁶⁰ Tanzania, The Finance Act, No. 8 of 2020. s 7 (a).

⁶¹ Tanzania, The Finance Act. No 8 of 2020 s. 7 (d)

⁶² Republic of South Africa, 'Companies Act', Pub. L. No. 71, 71 (2008). s 56 (2)(f)

⁶³ Tanzania, The Companies Act. No. 12 of 2002 s 115.

⁶⁴ The Institute of Company Secretaries of India, 'Companies Act, 2013: Share Capital and Debentures' (The Institute of Company Secretaries of India, 2013). para 2.

⁶⁵ Tanzania, The Companies Act. No. 12 of 2002 ss 107-108.

⁶⁶ Tanzania. The Companies Act s 102.

company through the payment of the principal sum and interest as agreed under debentures.

Individuals who aim to indirectly control the company, for example through shareholders, may not necessarily have their names registered as members of the company. This can be demonstrated by the fact that bearer shares are payable to the person who possesses them. This person does not need to have his name registered in the register of members of the company as a condition for him to be paid dividends. Also, through nominees, one may hold shares of the company for and on behalf of a person who is not identified unless the law prohibits it. Therefore, a member who holds a large number of shares has a great influence on the manner in which the affairs of the company is managed through appointment and removal of directors.

To close these loopholes in the law, new provisions on BO in Tanzania require not only registration of members of the company but also its BOs.⁶⁷ Consequently, it offers a room to firstly identify not only the registered members but also their nominees and those who hold the shares of the company at a particular time. Legal identification of these individuals helps to identify individuals or persons who are indirectly exerting influence on the manner in which the affairs of the company is being run. Therefore, it helps to easily identify a shadow director. Despite the intention of the law, its efficiency is inhibited by the fact that all BO data registered to the ORCs are confidential and shielded against public view.⁶⁸ However, company documents, for example, memorandum and articles of association, which contain similar particulars are registerable at the ORCs and are accessible to the public.⁶⁹ Limiting public from accessing these data affects their ability to report suspicious financial transactions even in informal sectors.

3.3 By updating records of registered beneficial interests

Generally, membership of a company is a mere contractual relation between the company and the member. A similar effect is demonstrated by the creditor - debtor relation arising out of the debentures held by companies.⁷⁰ Consequently, such relations may come to an end in various ways, for example, when an individual ceases to be a member of the company and is no longer able to influence the manner of management of the company, and is not expected to benefit by it anymore. However, new members of the company need to be registered and their particulars have to be sent to the ORCs. Similarly, new creditors will have to be registered and their interests protected. In a bid to identify those who may act as shadow director through indirect interests in the company, the register of members and BO has to be updated. The law states that:

⁶⁷ Tanzania, The Finance Act. No. 8 of 2020 s.11.

⁶⁸ Tanzania. Finance Act No. 8 of 2020 s 451B.

⁶⁹ Tanzania, The Companies Act. No. 12 of 2002 ss 15 and 18.

⁷⁰ The Institute of Company Secretaries of India, 'Companies Act, 2013: Share Capital and Debentures'. p. 51.

A company shall, where there are changes in the beneficial ownership of the company, give notice to the Registrar within thirty days of such changes.⁷¹

Taking the bearer shares and nominee as examples, it is expected that when the shares change hands, or when a new beneficiary of shares held under nominee relation is affected, the new statuses have to be filed with the ORCs. A comparable requirement is also noted in Nigeria where the regulations require companies to register those with significant control of the company at the time of incorporation and filing of returns.⁷²

To guarantee that every interested person is identified and registered, every company is empowered to serve a notice to any one believed by the company to have significant control, requiring such a person to furnish his particulars for effective registration. It is expected that such a person will act on the notice and the data will be registered. However, in the person resists or declines to provide the information, the company may issue a warning notice after the expiry of seven days. The company also is empowered to limit such powers of the person by entering the notice in the register of members while copying the office of the Commissioner, accompanied with a formal communication of the restriction notice to the person.⁷³ What this means is, the warned person may not exert influence aimed at directing what the company does any more. Furthermore, in case of a dispute, for example, relating to fraudulent trading, the person may be a potential candidate to be examined by the court due to his activities as a shadow director at the material time of his notification by the company.

The laws in Tanzania and Nigeria provide for a penalty in the nature of a fine in case of non-compliance with its provisions. The penalty in Tanzania is limited to monetary fine of not less than 5,000,000 TSHS and not more than 10,000,000 TSH.⁷⁴ In Nigeria, the general fine stands at 200,000 Naira and or imprisonment for a period of two years.⁷⁵ However, while the law in Nigeria fines even the person who refuses to furnish his information to the company that believes he exerts a significant control over its affairs, the law in Tanzania fines only the officials of the company that fails to furnish such information. Thus, as far as the registration of beneficial ownership in a company is concerned, company officials may bear liability for failure to declare the particulars of possible shadow directors or beneficial owners to the relevant bodies. This situation is possible because the law and regulations do not empower the company to request for

⁷¹ Tanzania, The Finance Act. No. 8 of 2020 s 12 (6).

⁷² Federal Republic of Nigeria, 'Persons with Significant Control Regulations' (2022). Regulation 3 (1).

⁷³ Federal Republic of Nigeria. Regulation 6 *vid* 7.

⁷⁴ United Republic of Tanzania, The Companies (Beneficial Ownership) Regulations. (2021) Regulation 10

⁷⁵ Federal Republic of Nigeria, Persons with Significant Control Regulations. (2022) Regulation 12 (9).

registration data from a possible shadow director. Unless the law is deterrent enough to discourage or impose a heavy penalty, potential criminals may still abuse the provisions.

The discussion above shows that through the new law on BO in Tanzania, shadow directors may be identified. Identification of shadow directors is mainly aimed at placing relevant legal obligations upon them mostly arising out of fraudulent trading that may transpire through illicit activities like money laundering and breach of directors' duties. Although the law has relevant provisions that may help to identify shadow directors, the provisions are however, not express. Furthermore, the law limits members of the public from accessing the BO data registered by the ORCs. Another challenge is the absence of a penalty to deter individuals who do not provide their data to company officials for onward transmission to the ORCs.

4. THE WAY FORWARD

The statutory position on which law should apply in Tanzania where there is a lacuna in the law or law is provided for under the Judicature and Application of laws Act. In particular, the Act states that:

...Court shall be exercised in conformity with the written laws which are in force in Tanzania on the date on which this Act comes into operation (including the laws applied by this Act) or which may hereafter be applied or enacted and, subject thereto and so far as the same shall not extend or apply, shall be exercised in conformity with the substance of the common law, the doctrines of equity and the statutes of general application in force in England on the twenty-second day of July, 1920,...⁷⁶

What this means is that, since the Companies Act is silent on the position of shadow directors, reliance has to be placed on common law principles. However, the discussion above has identified the rules regulating BO in Tanzania. In these rules, companies are required to register with the ORC among others, the individuals who exercise direct and or indirect control over the affairs of the company.⁷⁷ Consequently, these rules offer a narrow avenue through which shadow directors may be identified.

What is intriguing though is the fact that, at times, one may not exactly know if he is a shadow director to a particular company, up to and until when the court interprets given

⁷⁶ United Republic of Tanzania, Judicature and Application of laws Act. Cap 358 R.E 2019 s 2 (3).

⁷⁷ See para 3 above of this paper

facts and makes a decision that a specific individual is a shadow director.⁷⁸ This is to say that, even if the application of the BOs rules is to be relied upon, it may not cover all instances which may give rise to shadow directorship. It is therefore right to argue that firstly, the BO rules offer an avenue through which shadow directors may be identified through their registration owing to their direct or indirect control of the company. Secondly, reliance on common law principles to identify shadow directors should not be ignored due to the broad circumstances which may be taken into consideration by the court before holding that a situation of shadow directorship exists.

5. CONCLUSION

This paper is an attempt to examine the extent to which the Tanzanian rules on BOs may be relied to recognize and identify shadow directors. Through qualitative review of both primary and secondary sources this paper shows that, the existing legal rules on BO may be narrowly relied to recognize and or identify shadow directors in Tanzania. This is possible through the legal requirement of registration of all individuals who directly and or indirectly exercises significant influence on the direction of the company to the ORCs as BOs. However, unlike other common law countries such as; UK, Kenya, Nigeria and South Africa, Tanzania lacks an express provision on recognition and identification of shadow directors. It is also noted that the business laws on nature and type of data collected with respect to BOs in Tanzania treat such data as confidential. Preventing public access to these data may impede efforts not only to identify suspicious or illicit transactions, but also to identify the individuals who are behind such transactions especially in informal sectors. Consequently, this paper calls for review of business laws in Tanzania with the view to expressly recognize and provide a manner by which shadow directors may be identified in order to guarantee their accountability.

⁷⁸ See para 2.1 above of this paper.